

GROWTH AND SPORE FORMATION OF *BACILLUS NATTO* BY MICROWAVE ASSISTED CULTIVATION AT OPTIMUM TEMPERATURE AND THE EFFECT OF MICROWAVE POWER

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Introduction

As a high-efficiency and low-burden energy utilization method for reducing the burden on the global environment, the use of microwave energy for chemical reactions is attracting attention. In recent year, in addition to microwave effect on chemical reactions, many biological effects under microwave irradiation, including changes in microbial growth rate [1], maximum cellular mass [2], metabolic rate [1], genetic effects [3], [4], and morphological changes [5], [6] have been reported. Because the biological function, including metabolism, genetic function, and biological information transmission made happen by biomolecular interactions, namely chemical interaction, it is expected that biological effect under microwave irradiation made happen by microwave-enhanced chemistry. However, a clear conclusion has not yet been obtained. In any case, it can be said that these biological effects suggest the usefulness of microwaves for biotechnology such as high expression technology.

Our group has examined the microwave effects on microbial growth by some microorganism cultivation under microwave irradiation. For example, *Escherichia coli*, a representative model bacterium as gram-negative bacteria, and *Bacillus subtilis*, a representative model bacterium as gram-positive bacteria, were cultivated under microwave irradiation by using multi-mode microwave irradiator [2]. Each Bacterium were cultivated in cultivation fluid on optimum temperature (respectively, 37°C and 50°C) by heat transmission with *n*-Hexane, a small permittivity liquid, using double-tube vessel. As a result, it was confirmed that the maximum cellular mass of each bacterium depends on the microwave irradiation power. Additionally, it was found that the maximum cellular mass of each bacterium showed a convex upward curve against the microwave irradiation power. It can be said that this result suggests the existence of “optimum microwave power”. This means that there are conditions of microwave power that are favorable for bacterial growth. Moreover, it is expected that the existence of dependence on other bacterial growth parameter toward some microwave conditions, such as irradiation power, spatial distribution, and frequency. Therefore, in this study, our group researched the microwave effects on microbial growth rate, maximum cellular mass, and morphological changes, using linearly traveling microwave.

Material & Methods

Bacillus natto (*Bacillus subtilis* subsp. *subtilis* NBRC16449), which is used for the production of natto (a traditional Japanese fermented food), was cultivated in LB broth (Luria – Bertani liquid cultivation medium (Miller)) at its optimum temperature (30°C) under microwave irradiation. *Bacillus subtilis* has the ability to change morphology,

forming a certain percentage of spores that are resistant to various environmental stresses and hunger.

TE₁₀-mode traveling microwave (2.45 GHz) irradiator (GM Ic, J-SCIENCE LAB Co., Ltd.) was used to irradiate microwave toward cultivation fluid. This equipment can adjust the microwave irradiation power in the range of 0-300 W. In this experiment, microwave heating efficiency (ratio of absorbed power to irradiation power) was approximately 6.73%. Sheath thermocouple thermometer (YC520-33K, MC3000, CHINO Corporation) was used to measure the cultivation temperature. The cultivation temperature was maintained at the optimum temperature of *Bacillus natto* by heat transmission with *n*-Hexane, a small permittivity liquid, using double-tube vessel (Fig. 1). Absorptiometer (Ultrospec 3000 pro, amersham pharmacia biotech inc.) was used to measure optical density of cultivation fluid by 600 nm visible light (OD_{600nm}). Optical microscope (CKX53, Olympus Corporation) was used to observe normal (vegetative) cells in cultivating and spore cells after cultivating.

Fig. 1. Cultivation temperature-controlled microwave cultivation system.

As the experimental operation, melted 15 vol% glycerol stock fluid of *Bacillus natto* (OD_{600nm} = 1.1, log-phase) 100 μL was inoculated to LB broth 9.9 mL in double-tube vessel. Stirring by magnetic stirrer, *Bacillus natto* was cultivated under 0 (non-irradiation), 40, 120, 160 W microwave irradiation. During cultivating, for temporal observing, OD_{600nm} of cultivation fluid and number of colonies (NOC) of 10⁴ times diluted culture fluid (37°C, 48 hours incubation) were measured. After cultivation, for obtaining spore forming ratio, Wirtz-stained 10 times diluted cultivation fluid was observed.

As the analysis method for experimental data, in this study, the growth rate and maximum cellular mass were defined by using Gompertz curve's parameter (Respectively, *k* values and *G*_{max} values in the following Eq. 1).

$$G(t) = G_{\max} \exp(-A_0 / k \exp(-k(t - t_0))) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where *t* is cultivation time, *G*(*t*) is bacterial amount (in this case, OD_{600nm} or NOC), *t*₀ is initial time of bacterial growth, and *G*_{max}, *k*, *A*₀ are Gompertz parameters, respectively. It

is known that Gompertz curve can be used for fitting of microbial growth curve [7]. Additionally, for quantifying the spore forming ratio, self-made image analysis software was used. This software distinguishes between Wirtz-stained spore cells and vegetative cells using the HSV color space, and calculates the spore forming ratio from the occupied area of each cells by the following Eq.2.

$$R_s = 100 P_s / (P_v + P_s) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where R_s is the spore forming ratio, P_v , P_s is the summation of the number of pixels identified as vegetative or spore cells by the software, respectively. Moreover, following results of previous research [2], plots of k , G_{\max} , and R_s against microwave power were fitted by Gaussian curve, respectively.

Results & Discussion

The cultivation temperature of *Bacillus natto* and refrigerant temperature under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power are shown in following Fig. 2. From Fig. 2, it was confirmed that *Bacillus natto* were cultivated at approximately 30°C, their optimum temperature, during cultivating under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power.

Fig. 2. The cultivation temperature of *Bacillus natto* and refrigerant temperature under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power.

The growth curve of *Bacillus natto* and the logarithmic plot of the bacterial amount of *Bacillus natto* under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power are shown in following Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. From Fig. 4, regarding the plots related to OD_{600nm} , the plots related to the initial stage of cultivation are significantly deviated from the others. It is expected that this deviation of plot was caused from the amplified error due to the mathematical nature of the logarithmic function and the error in the initial concentration of bacterial cells. Therefore, for the 0, 40, 120 W data, k and G_{\max} were calculated using 4 plots excluding the first plot, and as $t_0 = 6$ [hours]. For the 160 W data, k and G_{\max} were calculated using 3 plots excluding the first 2 plots, and as $t_0 = 12$ [hours].

Fig. 3. The growth curve of *Bacillus natto* under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power.

Fig. 4. The logarithmic plot of the bacterial amount of *Bacillus natto* under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power.

According to above data, the k and G_{\max} were calculated as shown in following **Table 1** and **Fig. 5**. In **Table 1** and **Fig. 5**, where R is gas constant ($= 8.314 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$).

Table 1. k and G_{\max} of *Bacillus natto* under microwave irradiation of each power.

Microwave Irradiation Power [W]		0	40	120	160
Microwave Heating Efficiency [%]			6.73		
P_{MW} (Microwave Absorbed Power) [W]		0	2.69	8.08	10.8
t (Microwave Irradiation Time) [s]		108000			
System Average Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]		30.0	29.8	30.7	30.0
T (System Average Temperature) [K]		303.17	302.98	303.88	303.18
$P_{\text{MW}} t / (RT)$ [mol]		0	115	345	461
Gompertz Coefficient for $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ [-]	k	0.121	0.124	0.137	0.122
	G_{\max}	4.75	4.84	5.28	4.61
Gompertz Coefficient for NOC [-]	k	0.174	0.229	0.153	0.0800
	G_{\max}	256	98	178	88

Fig. 5. k and G_{\max} plot of *Bacillus natto* against microwave absorption power.

From **Fig. 5**, regarding $\text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$ data, it was confirmed that the k and G_{\max} depends on the microwave power. Additionally, these show a convex upward curve against the microwave power. Because definition of k and G_{\max} , it can be said that this result suggests the existence of “optimum microwave power” with respect to microbial growth rate and maximum cellular mass. Moreover, with compared to previous research [2] where using multi-mode microwave irradiator, this result suggests that the special distribution of microwaves does not affect bacterial growth. However, a clear conclusion related to the special distribution of microwaves has not yet been obtained. Regarding NOC data, k shows a convex upward curve against the microwave power too, but experimental data of G_{\max} does not show convex curves clearly. It is expected that this result was caused from the difficulty of colony counting due to the colonies shape of *Bacillus subtilis*.

For bacterial cellular morphology, a clear change regarding vegetative cells of *Bacillus natto* was not observed during cultivation under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power. With regard to the spore forming ratio of *Bacillus natto* after cultivation under microwave irradiation of each irradiation power, a clear change was also not observed (Fig. 6). However, according to Gaussian fitting for experimental data, the spore forming ratio shows a convex downward curve against the microwave power. This result can also be said to mean that there is a condition of microwave power that minimizes the stress felt by *Bacillus natto*. Therefore, the existence of “optimum microwave power” for bacterial morphological changes is suggested, but a clear conclusion has not yet been obtained.

Fig. 6. The spore forming ratio of *Bacillus natto* after microwave cultivation against microwave absorption power.

For *Bacillus subtilis*, it is known that the spore forming ability and the cellular density regulation were controlled by quorum sensing [8]. According to results in this study, it was suggested that the spore forming ratio and the maximum cellular mass of *Bacillus natto* were affected by microwave. Therefore, regarding microbial biological function, it is considered that microwave affects to the quorum sensing as microwave effect. This result suggested that biological microwave effect made happen by microwave-enhanced chemistry.

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